

Programme workshop COHESIVE

One Health collaboration dealing with new and (re)emerging zoonoses

Date November 26-27, 2018

Venue APHA-Weybridge, Woodham Lane, New Haw, Addlestone,
Surrey, KT15 3NB, United Kingdom

November 26th

10.30 – 11.30 Welcome and registration

11.30 – 11.45 Welcome by Dr Sarah Evans (APHA)

11.45 – 13.00 Plenary session

Introduction

Kitty Maassen, coordinator of COHESIVE (RIVM)

Introduction to COHESIVE as part of the One Health EJP and the aim of this first workshop in the process of drafting guidelines to help countries strengthening human-veterinary collaboration in the area of risk analysis of (emerging) zoonotic diseases, both within and between countries.

Sketching Europe in zoonotic risks

Speaker to be confirmed

There are many differences within Europe; different climates, landscapes, densities of people and animals. All these factors play a role in the risk for zoonotic diseases. An impression of the situation in Europe related to the risk of zoonotic diseases will be presented.

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

14.00 - 15.30 Plenary session

How are human- veterinary collaborations organised?

Experiences of four countries

United Kingdom - Dilys Morgan (PHE)

Italy - Gaia Scavia (ISS)

Nordic Countries - Elina Lahti (SVA)

Swiss Confederation - Jürg Danuser (BLV)

15.30 - 16.00 Coffee/tea break

16.00 - 16.30 Plenary session

Similarities and differences, results of the questionnaire

Kitty Maassen (RIVM)

Introduction to the interactive session about facing hurdles when working across domains

16.30 - 18.00 Interactive session

Working across domains, piece of cake?

All kind of obstacles may occur trying to work across domains in the area of risk analysis of new and (re)emerging zoonoses. For example legal, political, economic, geographical aspects or issues associated with data sharing. In this interactive session the most perceived barriers will be discussed in groups.

20.00 Dinner at DoubleTree Restaurant

Victoria Way, Woking, GU21 8EW

November 27th

9.00 - 11.00 Interactive session

Cross-border data sharing for public health

George Haringhuizen and Carolina dos Santos Ribeiro (RIVM)

An interactive session in which opinions and optimal solutions for political, ethical, economic, regulatory and legal barriers to cross-border sharing of genetic data from pathogens will be sought through analysis and discussion of eight real-time cases.

11.00 – 11.30 Coffee/tea break

11.30 – 12.15 Plenary session

Introduction to ECDC's Event Threat Management System, and related activities

Karin Johansson (ECDC)

ECDC is working on a new event and threat management system (ETMS). This signalling and response system, to which officially nominated food safety experts and animal health experts at the EU level (e.g. EFSA) and at the national level will have access, is replacing EPIS and will cover all public health events and threats. This system as well as other developments within ECDC will be presented.

12.15 - 13.15 Lunch

13.15 - 14.45 Interactive session

Cross-border collaborations

How are the current international networks organised, such as EURL/NRL? Are they operating in a One Health manner? How are new and (re)emerging zoonotic pathogens dealt with? What is the role of EFSA and ECDC and systems such as the old EPIS or new ETMS of ECDC? What can, and should, be improved? These and other questions will be discussed in this session.

14.45 - 15.15 Plenary session

Risk assessment; who, what (not), when and how?

Charlotte Cook (APHA)

The term risk assessment is used often, but what is it exactly and when is it used and how? A personal view and experiences are shared.

15.15 - 15.45 Coffee/tea break

15.45 - 17.15 Parallel Interactive sessions

1. Structured decision making: When to use which tool to assist risk assessment

Intended for people who are actually working with tools to assist risk assessment. There is a big maze of tools for risk assessment. In this workshop, we will make the first steps to making a decision tool for professionals which helps finding the right tool for the specific situation.

2. Towards the guidelines

One of the goals of the COHESIVE project is to provide guidelines to strengthen the collaboration between the human - veterinary (and environmental) domain, taking into account the differences between countries. The discussions during this meeting will be used as input to give further direction to the guidelines. We will gather input regarding the specific needs for setting up some kind of zoonosis structure. We will also explore the needs for actual support.

17.15 – 17.45 Plenary session

Wrap-up and farewell

Contact details

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